

OUTDOOR EXPOSURE OF ADVANCED COMPOSITES

Hiroshi Fukuda
(Science University of Tokyo, Chiba, Japan)

ABSTRACT

One of the problems of polymer matrix composites is a degradation due to moisture absorption or other environmental exposure. It is said epoxy matrix shows rather large degradation and many works have been done to make clear the environmental effects. The author and his colleagues are now doing a small-scale project of five-year outdoor exposure of several kinds of epoxy matrix composites. This paper reports the three-year exposure data.

INTRODUCTION

Since composite materials have large specific strength and specific modulus, they are widely used in various fields including aerospace application. Although polymer matrix composites have high corrosion-resistance, even these materials degrade during a long range.

A so-called hygrothermal effect is serious for polymer matrix composites and many works have been reported so far[1]. This subject of hygrothermal effect deals with the effects of moisture and temperature on polymer matrix composites.

Concerning effects of weather, an accelerated weathering test is popular where moisture, temperature and simulated sunshine are applied periodically and artificially. But actual outdoor exposure tests are few because it takes much time. Among them, the project of Boeing and NASA[2] is a large-scale work.

The author and his colleagues are now doing a small-scale test of five-year outdoor exposure of several kinds of epoxy matrix composites. In the present paper, the three-year outdoor exposure data of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP), glass fiber -- (GFRP), and their hybrids are reported.

LAMINATED PLATE

In the present test, the outdoor exposure of CFRP, GFRP, and two kinds of CF/GF hybrids are conducted. The terminologies of CF and GF are used here for carbon fiber and glass fiber.

Table 1 shows the outline of raw materials used in the experiment. Prepreg sheets of each fiber (cloth) were first made by impregnating epoxy resin. Laminated plates were then fabricated with hot-press method. The press condition was 130 C, 1 hour followed by two hours' after-cure at 130 C.

Table 1 Raw Materials

	CF	GF
fiber	8-harness satin woven fabric #6341 25 bundles/25mm	plain woven roving cloth R570 5.6 bundles/25mm
matrix	mixture of Epicote 828, Araldite 6071, etc. 120 C cure-type epoxy	
hardener	disiane-diamide DMP-30	

Seven plies of carbon or glass prepregs were used to make one CFRP or GFRP laminate. In addition, two kinds of hybrid plates were made by combining the above carbon- and glass- prepregs. The stacking sequence of one type of hybrid plate is CCGGGCC where C and G stand for carbon and glass prepreg, respectively; this hybrid is called here a HL hybrid which represents an interlaminated hybrid. Another type, HM plate, is CGCGCGC, which is expected to behave as an intermingled hybrid.

Both surfaces of these plates were coated with epoxy and polyurethane to prevent degradation. These laminated plates were supplied from Toray Company.

OUTDOOR EXPOSURE

The size of supplied laminates was 300mm x 300mm and four test plates with about 145mm x 130 mm were cut from one laminate. Three of these four test plates were outdoor-exposed at Sapporo, Tokyo and Kagoshima, which places represent north, central, and south part of Japan. Table 2 is the summary of test plates exposed for one, two and three years.

The test plates have been exposed on the roof of a building of each place. The angle of exposure is not controlled although the plate faces to the south. Although snow covers the roof from November to April in Spaaoro and ash of Sakurajima-volcano fall on the exposed plate in Kagoshima, the plates were left in natural condition, i.e., snow or ash was not removed.

RESULTS

1. Surface observation and weight change

The surface coating exposed to the sunshine was fairly damaged by only one year's exposure. This damage was aggresed with the exposure period. Any damage of the back-surface coating was observed. Figure 1 shows the surface of some samples after 3 years' exposure.

The weight of each test plate was measured before and after the outdoor exposure. Table 3 shows the weight change of each material, each place and each exposure

Table 2 Thickness and Volume Fraction of Laminated Plates

		CFRP	GFRP	HL	HM
stacking sequence		(C) ₇	(G) ₇	CCGGGCC	CGCGCGC
#1	thick.(mm)	2.49	2.50	2.59	2.91
	volume fraction(%)	65.1	67.2	C 33.7 G 25.4	C 35.7 G 26.9
#2	thick.	2.58	2.54	2.76	2.77
	V _f	64.2	67.1	C 32.2 G 24.2	C 33.0 G 24.8
#3	thick.	2.61	2.49	2.75	2.65
	V _f	63.6	66.8	C 33.9 G 25.5	C 33.9 G 25.5

Fig.1 Material surface of exposed plate

period. Generally speaking, the weight of a plate increased after one year's exposure and decreased thereafter. For some plates, the weight decrease at 3 years' exposure was too large. This would be due to the peel-out of the coating material.

2. Four-point bending

The sunshine and rain drop would affect the matrix and the fiber-matrix interface rather than the fiber itself. Then a four-point bending and a short-beam interlaminar shear test were conducted by which the effect of outdoor exposure is expected clearer comparing to other evaluation such as tension test.

A. Bending test

A four-point bending test was conducted in accordance with ASTM D 790-71. The span length was 90mm and the span of the loading noses was L/3 where L is the span of the supporting noses, 90mm. The crosshead speed was set to 5mm/min for failure test. Five specimens under one exposure condition were tested.

Although a sound of crack were heard at fairly early stage of load application (at 1/2 to 1/3 of maximum load), no distinct change was observed at this stage and the load-deflection curve was still straight. By further application of load, transverse cracks were observed on the compression surface between loading noses followed by the fiber failure and delamination. Figure 2 shows some examples of the load-deflection curves.

Fig.2 Load-deflection curve

Table 3 Weight Change (%)

		CFRP	GFRP	HL	HM
Tokyo	1 year	0.25	0.23	0.26	0.27
	2 years	-0.11	-0.14	-0.02	0.26
	3 years	-0.50	-1.46	-0.06	-0.11
Kagoshima	1 year	-0.12	0.24	0.34	0.34
	2 years	-0.45	-1.50	-0.03	-0.02
	3 years	-0.59	-1.10	-0.18	-0.72
Sapporo	1 year	0.30	0.21	0.28	0.22
	2 years	-0.20	-0.13	-0.12	-0.13
	3 years	-0.36	-1.33	-0.27	-0.19

Fig.3 Yearly change of Young's modulus

B. Bending modulus

From a small deformation theory of a beam, the bending modulus is calculated by

$$E = \frac{23 \times 10^3}{1296I} \left(\frac{P}{\delta} \right) \quad (1)$$

where P is the applied load and δ denotes the deflection at the center of the span.

Figure 3 shows the average value of Young's moduli. Although there are some scatters, the bending modulus of each material after exposure became larger than that before exposure. The rate of increase was 9%-32%. No distinct difference among exposure locations was observed so far.

C. Bending strength

The following equation was used to calculate the bending strength:

$$\sigma_b = \frac{P_{max} \cdot l}{bh^2} \quad (2)$$

The results are shown in Fig.4. The bending strength increased for one or two years' exposure; after that period, the strength decreased. The strength retention was from 99% to 108%.

D. Estimation of modulus of hybrid composites

If we know the properties of GFRP and CFRP, properties of GF/CF hybrids should be estimated.

Assuming that Kirchhoff's hypothesis holds for HL hybrids, the bending modulus of HL hybrids can be calculated as follows:

$$E_{HL} = E_{CFRP} (1-\alpha^3) + E_{GFRP} \alpha^3 \quad (3)$$

where α is the fraction of GFRP.

If carbon fibers and glass fibers of HM hybrid are mingled homogeneously, the modulus will be calculated by

$$E_{HM} = E_{CFRP} (1-\alpha) + E_{GFRP} \alpha \quad (4)$$

But if we must account for the stacking sequence of the HM hybrid, the modulus should be calculated by

$$E_{HM} = E_{GFRP} \alpha^3 + E_{CFRP} (\beta^3 - \alpha^3) + E_{GFRP} (\gamma^3 - \beta^3) + E_{CFRP} (\delta^3 - \gamma^3) \quad (5)$$

where $\alpha, \beta, \gamma,$ and δ are shown in Fig.5.

Fig.4 Yearly change of bending strength

Fig.5 HM hybrid

Table 4 Estimation of Bending Modulus of Hybrid Composites (GPa)

	CFRP exp.	GFRP exp.	HL		HM		
			exp.	theo1	exp.	theo2	theo3
no exposure	49.8	22.4	47.2	47.6	41.7	38.0	41.8
1 year Tokyo	54.5	25.8	49.8	52.2	48.9	42.2	46.2
	57.4	25.7	48.9	54.9	49.4	43.8	48.2
	55.6	26.9	50.0	53.3	47.8	43.3	47.3
2 year Tokyo	53.1	25.8	49.9	51.0	45.2	41.4	45.2
	56.1	29.9	53.4	54.0	46.0	44.9	48.5
	54.3	27.6	50.7	52.2	46.3	42.8	46.6
3 year Tokyo	55.0	28.4	55.2	52.9	45.2	43.6	47.3
	58.2	29.2	57.4	55.9	44.8	45.8	49.8
	54.4	29.6	55.2	52.4	45.7	43.8	47.2

[note] theo1: eq.(3), theo2: eq.(4), theo3: eq.(5)

Table 5 Estimation of Bending Strength of Hybrid Composites (MPa)

	CFRP exp.	GFRP exp.	HL		HM	
			exp.	theo.	exp.	theo.
no exposure	647	385	621	614	469	542
1 year Tokyo	732	417	673	670	526	657
	724	408	666	614	536	624
	727	405	681	654	547	625
2 year Tokyo	692	478	672	650	510	589
	734	478	649	700	527	602
	707	460	659	660	527	602
3 year Tokyo	678	475	671	681	483	557
	666	428	617	657	481	513
	659	412	639	669	469	554

[note] theo: eq.(6)

Table 4 shows the experimental values and the theoretical predictions. For HL hybrids, the difference between experimental values and the corresponding theoretical values is less than 5% except for one case (Kagoshima, one year exposure). Then it may be concluded that the bending modulus of HL hybrids can be estimated by eq.(3).

For HM hybrids, the value predicted by eq.(4) is fairly smaller (at most 14%) than the experimental value. On the other hand, the difference between experimental values and theoretical values by means of eq.(5) is within 5%. This indicates that the present HM hybrid is not a real intermingled hybrid but a kind of interlaminated hybrid.

E. Estimation of strength of hybrid composites

In most cases of the present CF/GF hybrids, the failure initiated from a compressive failure of the outermost carbon layer. Thus the bending strength of hybrid composites will be calculated by

$$\sigma_{b,H} = \frac{E_H}{E_{CFRP}} \sigma_{b,CFRP} \quad (6)$$

where σ_b and E are, respectively, the bending strength and the bending modulus, and the subscripts H and CFRP indicate hybrid and CFRP.

The predicted values are shown in Table 5 together with experimental data. For HL hybrids, eq.(6) may be useful to predict the bending strength of HL hybrids although there remains some scattering. On the other hand, eq.(6) predicts somewhat higher

values than experimental data for HM hybrids; further refinement of strength theory will be needed for HM hybrids.

3. Interlaminar shearing test

A short beam test was conducted in accordance with ASTM D 2344-72 with the span length of 15mm and the width of specimen, 6mm. The interlaminar shearing strength was evaluated by

$$\tau_{\max} = \frac{3P_{\max}}{4bh} \quad (7)$$

Results are shown in Fig.6, which tendency is similar to the case of bending strength.

CONCLUSIONS

Four kinds of composites are now under outdoor exposure. According to the results up to three years' exposure, all the bending strength and modulus, and the interlaminar shearing strength retained the initial values nevertheless the surface coating was much damaged. It has also been made clear that the strength and modulus of CF/GF hybrid composites are predictable from the properties of the constituents, CFRP and GFRP.

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Fig.6 Yearly change of interlaminar shearing strength